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Carbon Stock Estimation in the Nusawiru Mangrove Ecosystem, Pangandaran Regency, Indonesia

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to estimate carbon stocks in mangrove ecosystems in the Nusawiru area, Pangandaran. Research on carbon stocks, particularly in the Nusawiru mangrove ecosystem, is important for understanding their vital role in climate change mitigation and maintaining coastal ecosystem balance, as well as providing the data and information needed for sustainable coastal ecosystem management and conservation. The existing mangrove condition in Nusawiru covers an area of 5 ha with mangrove coverage of 10 ha, dominated *Nypa fruticans* by the species. The method used in this study is a descriptive method. Field data were obtained through mangrove biomass measurements and carbon stock analysis using an allometric approach. Samples were collected from 5 stations. The results of the study indicate that carbon stocks in the Nusawiru mangrove area vary based on vegetation type and tree density. The estimated average carbon stock reached 355.12 tonnes C/ha, indicating the area's potential as a significant carbon sink, given the high biomass in the area. There are several areas experiencing a decline in quality, likely due to pressure from human activities.

Keywords: carbon stock, climate change, mitigation, conservation, ecosystem, mangrove, Nusawiru, Pangandaran, management

1. INTRODUCTION

Mangroves are plants in coastal ecosystems that have unique characteristics, are tolerant to salinity [18], have high productivity [5], have complex, diverse, and heterogeneous ecosystem characteristics, and are commonly found in tropical and subtropical climates [15].

The distinctive characteristics of mangrove ecosystems provide mangrove forests with several physical, biological, socio-economic, and cultural functions for coastal communities. In terms of their physical functions, mangroves serve as protective barriers for coastal areas, reducing abrasion, waves, wind, seawater intrusion, and the impact of major storms. The structural configuration of mangrove trees, including their trunk and root systems, helps disperse wave energy and reduce wave height [6]. Indonesia, Brazil, Malaysia, and Papua New Guinea are known to account for 50% of the world's mangrove ecosystem area [23]. Mangrove forests in Indonesia are estimated to store 1,528.8 MgC/ha [19] and four times more than other tropical forests [14].

Every year, approximately 137 to 636 km² of mangrove ecosystems are lost globally, representing 0.16 – 0.39% of the total ecosystems lost per year [8]. Mangrove ecosystem damage in Indonesia is very high and has threatened carbon reserves for the past six decades [10]. The high rate of mangrove forest destruction in Indonesia has caused carbon emissions into the atmosphere amounting to 42% of global emissions, estimated at 0.15 – 1.02 Pg CO₂e per year, while global blue carbon emissions are equivalent to 3 – 19% of total global emissions [14]. The main causes of mangrove deforestation include urban development, aquaculture, mining, and overexploitation of timber, fish, crustaceans, and molluscs [1]. In addition to aquaculture, tourism development is one of the human activities that threaten the existence of mangrove forests [3, 22]. Interest in mangrove-based ecotourism activities is currently on the rise. Such activities have positive impacts on the local economy; however, unsustainable and irresponsible ecotourism, such as clearing land for tourist facilities, can reduce the rate of carbon absorption by mangroves [2]. Conversely, ecotourism in mangrove areas combined with conservation efforts can support climate change mitigation efforts [16].

Measuring carbon stocks in mangrove ecosystems can help assess their ecosystem services and provide a reference for long-term mangrove management [16]. Carbon storage in mangrove ecosystems is found in biomass (above-ground and below-ground biomass) and soil, which stores carbon for longer periods than tree biomass [13]. This stored carbon can be disturbed and released more quickly when mangrove land is converted or cleared [22]. Given the high threat to mangrove ecosystems along the coast, which contribute to carbon emissions into the atmosphere, mitigation efforts in the form of mangrove planting (rehabilitation) are needed. Pangandaran Regency is located in the southern coastal area of West Java. In 2018, the mangrove area in this regency reached 165 hectares, with 10 hectares in rehabilitation status. Pangandaran Regency is a developing regency, so to provide coastal resilience for local communities, development must be supported by sustainable coastal environmental protection. One area with mangrove potential in Pangandaran Regency is Cijulang Village, particularly in Nusagede Hamlet, where the mangrove ecosystem area has been developed as an ecotourism site known as Nusawiru Mangrove Ecotourism. This study was conducted with the aim of estimating carbon stocks in mangrove ecosystems in the Nusawiru area of Pangandaran. By understanding the relationship between carbon stocks and tourism activities, we can take steps to minimise negative impacts and maximise positive impacts, so that tourism can contribute to environmental conservation and climate change mitigation.

2. METHODOLOGY

2. 1. Study Area

The research was conducted in the Nusawiru mangrove area, Cijulang Subdistrict, Pangandaran Regency. The coordinates for Nusawiru Mangrove Ecotourism in Nusa Gede Hamlet, Cijulang Village, are 7°39'58.6" S - 108°33'38.0" E. The research was conducted in September 2024. Data collection was conducted at 5 stations:

Stasiun 1: 108°29'31" E - 7°43'33.82"S

Stasiun 2: 108°29'29.28"E - 7°43'35.62"S

Stasiun 3: 108°29'28.53"E - 7°43'39.62"S

Stasiun 4: 108°29'33.60"E - 7°43'39.46"S

Stasiun 5: 108°29'34.67"E - 7°43'42.96"S

Figure 1. Study area – Nusawiru Region.

2. 2. Method Research

This study utilised a quantitative descriptive research method. Mangrove data collection was conducted using 20-metre diameter transects. A midpoint was established, and straight lines were drawn 10 metres north, east, and west from that point. Diameter transects were selected because data collection was based on existing coordinates. Data collection was carried

out taking into account the tides, namely when the water level was at its lowest ebb to facilitate data collection.

2. 2. 1. Carbon Stock Analysis

Estimating mangrove carbon stocks requires several data points, such as DBH (diameter at breast height, cm), DS (diameter of base), DB (diameter of stem), classification of mangroves and non-mangroves, documentation of mangrove tree parts (roots, trunks and/or leaves) and identification of mangrove species. The data obtained is then processed and analysed quantitatively using mangrove biomass above ground (Aboveground Biomass, AGB) estimated using allometric equations. Carbon stock estimation is also used to measure the ability of mangroves to absorb and store carbon from the atmosphere as a mitigation measure against disasters caused by climate change.

Allometric calculations were performed using the DBH and DS data obtained. The mangrove tree circumference data was first converted into tree diameter, which could then be used in allometric calculations. The biomass data was then multiplied by 0.47 to estimate the carbon stock in tree biomass [9].

$$Cb = B \times \% C \text{ Organic}$$

notes : Cb = carbon stock (kg)

B = total iomass (kg)

% C organic = Percentage value of carbon 0,47

Carbon stocks can be estimated from tree biomass because 45 – 50% of tree biomass is carbon [20].

Table 1. Formula Aboveground Biomass (AGB).

Spesies	Formula AGB (kg)
<i>Avicennia marina</i>	$W_{top} = 0,308 \times DBH^{2.11}$ [4]
<i>Nypa fruticans</i>	$W_{top} = 0,098 \times DBH^{1.4934}$ [24]
	$W_{top} = 0,222 \times DS^{2.7048}$ [24]
<i>Rhizophora mucronata</i>	$W_{top} = 0,128 \times DBH^{2.60}$ [7]
<i>Sonneratia alba</i>	$W_{top} = 0,157 \times DBH^{2.101}$ [12]

Notes : Wtop: Above-ground biomass (kg); DBH: Diameter of tree measured at breast height

DBH and DS data were collected through direct measurements on each mangrove tree. Mangrove trees with DBH >5 cm were selected for data collection. Species identification was carried out to determine the appropriate AGB calculation for each species.

2. 2. 2. Analysis of Mangrove Cover in Nusawiru

Normalised Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) is a calculation on an image used to determine the level of greenness as a starting point for dividing vegetation and land cover areas. The NDVI value is obtained by combining the NIR band with the red band reflected by plants and is written in the equation [21] as follows:

$$NDVI = \frac{NIR - Red}{NIR + Red}$$

Notes: NDVI : Normal Difference Vegetation Index

NIR : Near Infrared Band

Red : Red Band

The results of mapping the distribution of mangrove vegetation in the Nusawiru area, Cijulang District, Pangandaran Regency, West Java, are shown in Figure 2. The visualisation of mangrove vegetation density in the Nusawiru area based on Normalised Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) values was carried out using remote sensing technology with Sentinel-2 satellite imagery and data from the Copernicus website (<https://browser.dataspace.copernicus.eu/>).

Figure 2. Distribution of Mangrove Vegetation in Nusawiru Area.

Field data collected from 29 coordinate points in the Nusawiru area revealed the presence of true mangrove species such as *Avicennia marina*, *Rhizophora mucronata*, *Nypa fruticans*, and *Sonneratia alba*, as well as non-mangrove vegetation in the form of *Cocos nucifera* (Figure 2).

Table 2. Vegetation Index Value.

No	Vegetation Index Value	Level of Greenery
1	0.40 - 1	High vegetation
2	0.25 - < 0.40	Moderate vegetation
3	0.03 - < 0.025	Low vegetation
4	-1 – 0.03	No vegetation

Vegetation index values in the Nusawiru mangrove area, Cijulang. The results obtained from the ground truth area at five stations with values ranging from 0.390 to 0.515 indicate that vegetation density in the Nusawiru Mangrove area is moderate to high.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3. 1. AGB (*Aboveground Biomass*)

1). Station 1 (108°29'31" E - 7°43'33.82"S)

The mangrove species growing at station 1 is dominated by *Nypa fruticans*, which is the main component of the mangrove forest ecosystem, with a population reaching 30% of the total mangrove forest area. Station 1 has a diverse range of nipah DBH values, with the highest reaching 258 cm and DS ranging from 11 cm to 23 cm. The nipah biomass at this station is also diverse in terms of both DBH and DS, as is its carbon stock value, which is directly proportional to its density. The density of mangrove stands affects biomass value, carbon content, and carbon dioxide absorption capacity [11]. The higher the mangrove stand density, the greater the biomass produced, which in turn increases carbon content and carbon absorption capacity.

Figure 3. Estimated Carbon Stock at Station 1.

Sonneratia alba shows a high degree of diversity in DBH and DS values for each tree, reaching up to 69 cm. The highest AGB value for *Sonneratia alba* was recorded at 1146 kg for a tree with a DB of 69 cm, while the highest carbon uptake value for *Sonneratia alba* was recorded at 539 kg.

Figure 3 above shows that the carbon stock of each tree varies. The first and fifth trees have fairly high carbon stocks of 430 kg and 539 kg, respectively. Trees 6 to 14 show a decrease in carbon stock absorption, with the lowest value being 79 kg. Carbon absorption increases in the 20th tree, reaching 361 kg.

This pattern shows that only a few mangroves contain high carbon stocks, while most mangroves have lower carbon stocks than others. Factors influencing differences in carbon absorption values in mangroves include diameter and density in a given area.

Station 1 has an NDVI value of 0.390, indicating that the vegetation has moderate greenness and moderate density. At Station 1, two types of mangrove trees were found, totaling 20 individuals, with *Nypa fruticans* being the dominant species. There were 13 individuals of this species, and there were 7 individuals of *Sonneratia alba*, which had a carbon absorption capacity of 11.24 kg/m².

2). Station 2 (108°29'29.28"E - 7°43'35.62"S)

Station 2 recorded estimated carbon stocks in two mangrove species, *Nypa fruticans* and *Rhizophora mucronata*. The station is located at 108°29'29.28'E and 7°43'35.62'S. Allometric calculations at Station 2 identified two mangrove species: *Nypa fruticans* and *Rhizophora mucronata*. Station 2 is still dominated by *Nypa fruticans* as the most abundant species in the station, with 17 individual trees. The other species found is *Rhizophora mucronata*, with only 3 trees in the station.

The results of trunk diameter measurements showed highly variable trunk values. The variation in stem diameter showed DBH values ranging from 167 cm to 270 cm, with branch diameters ranging from 10 to 21 cm. The highest wet stem weight reached 419 grams on a tree with a DBH of 270 cm, while the highest wet branch weight was recorded at 837 grams on a tree with a DBH of 190 cm. In terms of dry weight, the stem with a DBH of 250 cm had the highest value, at 1,491 grams, while the dry weight of the branch reached a maximum of 701 grams on the same tree.

Figure 4. Estimated Carbon Stock at Station 2.

Rhizophora mucronata species with the highest DBH was recorded at 8 cm with an AGB of 43 kg. The largest carbon stock was recorded at 20 kg. The relatively small estimated carbon stock was due to the low DBH value of *Rhizophora mucronata*.

The NDVI mapping results for station 2 have a vegetation index value of 0.484, indicating that the greenness level at this station is moderate with a not too high density, but the vegetation condition is in a High state.

The highest mangrove carbon stock value of 197 kg was found in the eighth tree at station 2, while the lowest value of 5 kg was found in the twentieth tree. A total of 20 mangrove trees were found, 17 of which were *Nypa fruticans* and three of which were *Rhizophora mucronata*. The mangroves have a carbon absorption capacity of 7.57 kg/m².

3). Station 3 (108°29'28.53"E - 7°43'39.62"S)

At station 3, only the *Nypa fruticans* species was found. The stem diameter (DBH) of this species ranged from 151 cm to 241 cm, whereas the stem diameter of *Nypa fruticans* ranged from 11 cm to 28 cm. The maximum weight of the upper stem section was 354 cm, while the stem weight reached 1,882 cm.

The dry weight of the trunk was 499.0 g for a tree with a trunk diameter of 223 cm and 942 g for a tree with a stem diameter of 2004 cm. Trees with larger stems and branches tend to have a greater capacity to store carbon. At station 3, the *Nypa* with the highest DBH and DS was 241 cm and 24 cm respectively, with an AGB of 354 kg and an estimated carbon stock value of 166.2 kg.

Figure 5. Estimated Carbon Stock at Station 4.

With an NDVI value of 0.515, it can be concluded that Station 3 has high levels of greenness, with optimal density and vegetation conditions. The estimated carbon stock value per tree at Station 3 is relatively consistent, ranging from 82.7 to 166.2 kg. However, the 16th tree has a carbon stock value of 499 kg, indicating a higher absorption rate than the other trees. Eighteen *Nypa fruticans* individuals were found at Station 3, with an average carbon absorption capacity of 8.91 kg/m².

4). Station 4 (108°29'33.60"E - 7°43'39.46"S)

Station 4 was located at 108°29'33.60"E and 7°43'39.46"S, where two species of mangrove were identified. *Nypa fruticans* and *Avicennia marina*. The mean DBH of *Nypa fruticans* is 196 cm, with a maximum of 278 cm, and an estimated carbon content of 206 kg for the tree with the largest DBH, and a DS of up to 28 cm. The wet weight of the upper part of the *Nypa fruticans* stem is 438 grams for a stem with a diameter of 278 cm. The maximum weight capacity of the upper part of the stem is 1,882 grams, with a diameter of 27 cm. The maximum recorded weight of the dry stem was 182 gr for a tree with a diameter of 387 cm. Concurrently, the maximum weight of dry branches was documented as 856 gr for a tree with a trunk diameter of 1822 cm. This variation demonstrates the close relationship between the tree's physical size, encompassing its trunk and branches, and its carbon storage capacity.

The estimated carbon stock in *Avicennia marina* biomass has been found to exceed that of *Nypa fruticans*. The maximum recorded carbon stock for *Avicennia marina* was determined to be 5573 grams. This is related to its age, diameter and greater carbon storage capacity compared to two other mangrove species. *Avicennia marina* exhibits a relatively extensive diameter range, with the maximum recorded value standing at 149 cm and an AGB of 11,857 kg. Consequently, the estimated carbon absorption capacity of *Avicennia marina* is 5,573 kg, yet this substantial figure has not been calculated in total.

Figure 6. Estimated Carbon Stock at Station 4.

NDVI value of 0.466 indicates that the vegetation at Station 4 is not completely dense and has some areas with sparse vegetation or vegetation under stress. This relatively low NDVI value may be consistent with the low carbon stock in most trees in this area, except for a few large trees that are exceptions. NDVI values in the range of 0.4 to 0.5 indicate vegetation with moderate greenness, which generally indicates vegetation that is not very dense or plants that are growing normally but not at their maximum potential. This could be due to differences in the size or health of trees in this area.

The variation in estimated carbon stock values ranges from 81 to 937 kg, especially for trees in ranks 1 to around 14. A sharp increase occurs in trees in ranks 15 and 16 of the mangrove

species *Avicennia marina*. *Avicennia marina* trees in ranks 15 and 16 show estimated carbon stock values of approximately 4,247 kg and 5,573 kg. At station 4, two mangrove species were found in a transect consisting of 22 trees, dominated by *Nypa fruticans* with 16 individuals, followed by 6 *Avicennia marina* trees with a carbon absorption capacity of 43.14 kg/m².

5). Station 5 (108°29'34.67"E - 7°43'42.96"S)

Station 5 is located at 108°29'34.67'E and 7°43'42.96'S. At this station, 26 mangrove trees were found, of the *Nypa fruticans* and *Avicennia marina* species. The *Avicennia marina* species at this station was recorded as 8 trees. Station 5 is dominated by the *Nypa fruticans* species. The DBH value of *Nypa fruticans* at this station has the highest value of 273, with the highest AGB value of 426 cm. The *Avicennia marina* species at this station has a higher number of trees compared to the previous station. The DBH value recorded was 102 cm with the highest AGB value of 5330 kg. The carbon absorption capacity at station 5 reached 2505 kg, which is considered high. The NDVI value at station 5 was 0.466. An NDVI value in this range indicates vegetation with moderate greenness, indicating the presence of vegetation but not too dense or in optimal condition. This value indicates that the plants at this location are growing in moderate conditions, or there may be areas with sparse vegetation, causing the NDVI value to not be too high.

Figure 7. Estimated Carbon Stock at Station 5.

The 18th tree had a carbon stock of more than 2500, and several trees in the 20th to 23rd positions had carbon stocks ranging from 500 to 1000. This pattern shows that only a few trees at Station 5 contributed significantly to the carbon stock, while most of the other trees had low carbon stocks. At Station 5, 28 mangrove trees of two species were found in the transect, dominated by 20 *Nypa fruticans* trees and 8 *Avicennia marina* trees, which have a carbon absorption capacity of 35.67 kg/m².

3. 2. Aboveground Biomass Nusawiru Area

Allometric calculations and carbon stock estimates showed varying results. The calculations were directly proportional to the number of trees and stem diameter. The total calculations for each station can be seen in the following table:

Table 3. Calculation of Aboveground Biomass in the Nusawiru Region.

Number Station	Total Tree Biomass (kg)	Total Tree Weight/area (kg/m²)	Estimated Carbon Stock (ton/ha)
Station 1	3.529	11,24	112,38
Station 2	2.378	7,6	76
Station 3	2.799	9	89
Station 4	13.546	43,14	431
Station 5	11.201	35,7	357
Total	33.453,46	106,68	1.065,38

Secara umum dapat diamati bahwa total biomassa pohon tertinggi berada pada stasiun 4 (13546 kg), total berat pohon per luas area tertinggi berada di stasiun 4 (43,14 kg/m²) dan estimasi stok karbon tertinggi berada pada stasiun 1 (112,38). Kawasan Nusawiru memiliki variasi dalam kemampuan menyimpan karbon berdasarkan total biomassa pohon dan kerapatan vegetasi di setiap stasiun. Stasiun dengan biomassa tinggi (seperti Stasiun 4) memiliki kontribusi yang signifikan terhadap stok karbon kawasan. Secara keseluruhan, dengan total biomassa sebesar 33.453,46 kg dan stok karbon yang signifikan, kawasan ini merupakan aset penting dalam pelestarian lingkungan, mitigasi perubahan iklim, dan pengelolaan ekosistem pesisir yang berkelanjutan.

Land cover changes in the Nusawiru area, such as the construction of Nusawiru Airport and its supporting facilities, residential or commercial facilities, and tourist facilities, have the potential to trigger an increase in greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. The reduction in the number of trees and vegetation results in a decrease in the ability to absorb carbon from the atmosphere. Carbon footprints are not only generated by land cover change activities but also caused by community and tourist activities. Increased GHG emissions released into the atmosphere are due to excessive use of air conditioning, inefficient electricity use, and so on. Land cover change is a crucial factor in the development of activities that cause an increase in carbon footprints [17].

Therefore, efforts are needed to maintain ecosystem balance, especially by preventing the reduction of protected areas. In addition, concrete steps must be taken to preserve protected areas, including:

- 1) Enforcing regulations on space usage, especially in protected areas; and

- 2) Promoting sustainable tourism, namely promoting environmentally friendly transportation options, energy-efficient accommodation, and tourism activities that do not damage the environment.
- 3) Investing in renewable energy, namely using renewable energy sources to meet energy needs in tourist areas.
- 4) Conserving and restoring ecosystems, namely by protecting and restoring carbon-storing ecosystems such as forests and wetlands.
- 5) Public education and awareness, namely by increasing public understanding of the impact of carbon emissions and the importance of maintaining carbon stocks.
- 6) Developing environmentally-based local communities, both in terms of strengthening institutions and developing human resource skills, as well as collaborating with various parties to implement programmes.

Conservation efforts need to be carried out continuously and sustainably by various parties, including local governments, academics, local communities, and non-profit organisations involved in environmental preservation. Some activities, such as mangrove rehabilitation, tree planting, and reforestation, are merely formalities with minimal follow-up measures. The environment is increasingly degraded, yet efforts to address this issue are minimal. This poses a threat to the sustainability of coastal areas from various hazards and the impacts of climate change. By understanding the relationship between carbon stocks and land clearing, particularly for tourism activities, we can take steps to minimise negative impacts and maximise positive impacts, thereby enabling tourism to contribute to environmental conservation and climate change mitigation.

4. CONCLUSION

Based on the research results, it can be concluded that the estimated carbon stock of Nusawiru mangroves is directly proportional to the area or density of mangroves. The highest estimated carbon stock was found at station 4, amounting to 431 tonnes/ha, with a tree biomass value of 13,546 kg and a total tree weight/area value of 43.14 kg/m². The types of mangroves found in the Nusawiru mangrove area are quite diverse. The types that were successfully found and identified are *Rhizophora mucronata*, *Sonneratia alba*, *Nypa fruticans*, and *Avicennia marina*. The most dominant type in this area is *Nypa fruticans*.

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